

THE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONSUMPTION OF LOCAL PRODUCTS IN MOROCCO

LES FACTEURS INFLUANT SUR LA CONSOMMATION DE PRODUITS LOCAUX AU MAROC

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Abstract

Nowadays, Moroccan consumers have a hyper-choice of food products, whereby they have to choose between too many types of foreign or local ones. This hyper-choice is due to globalization's impact, notably from the occident. Thus, panoply of information is presented for the consumer. Using semi-conducted interviews, it turned out that the abundance or absence of information influences the knowledge and involvement of Moroccans towards the consumption of local products.

Keywords : Involvement – knowledge – information – local products – food consumption

Résumé

De nos jours, les consommateurs marocains font face à un hyper-choix au niveau des produits alimentaires, ce qui les oblige à choisir entre plusieurs types de produits étrangers ou locaux. Cette diversité de choix est due à l'impact de la mondialisation, notamment occidentale. Ainsi, une panoplie d'informations est présentée aux consommateurs. A l'aide des entretiens semi-directifs, il s'est avéré que l'abondance ou l'absence d'informations influence la connaissance ainsi l'implication des marocains envers la consommation des produits de terroir.

Mot clés : Implication – connaissance – information – produits de terroir – la consommation alimentaire.

Introduction

The Moroccan market knows an invasion of foreign products, which represents fierce competition for the local ones. This has contributed to many changes in the food consumption habits of Moroccans people. We live an occidental consumption style in an African country, in other words, there is a bipolarity of consumption in our country. For example, food imports have increased by an average of 15% per year since 2005 according to the United Nations Comtrade database, among the products produced by Morocco and the same time imported from foreign countries are olive oil and dates.

According to a recent study in Morocco concerning the consumption of local products by (Bouallala, 2018), olive oil, and dates are the most consumed local products. This result encourages us to find out if Moroccan consumers prefer local or foreign Olive oil and dates, by exploring the factors of their choices.

The local products are seen as a vehicle for economic and social development, especially, in the marginalized regions. They have been encouraged and assisted by several organizations, like the ministry of agriculture and maritime fisheries has reserved a prominent place for local products in its new agricultural development strategy: the Green Morocco Plan (PMV) launched by his Majesty the King in Meknes in April 2008. This initiative encourages the creation of cooperatives through grants and organizational support.

In 2017/18, the area planted with olive trees reached 1.045 million hectares, i.e. nearly 300,000 ha since the launch of the Green Morocco Plan. Production, although erratic, also increased to nearly 2 million tons in the 2018/19 campaign, an increase of 28% over the previous campaign (Harbouze et al., 2019,p. 35).

As its remarkable Morocco has satisfying Olive's oil! Which means the cooperatives have enough products to promote? The mean question we should ask is if the Moroccan Consumer is involved in the process of buying those products from the Moroccan cooperatives or prefer the foreigners one? In other terms is the Moroccan consumer knows about those cooperatives?

Our research aims to answer this question to understand the behavior of the Moroccan consumer. Thus, by exploring the knowledge and the involvement of Moroccans towards local products. Choosing as case: Olive's oil.

1 Literature review

1.1. The consumption of local products in Morocco: hypermodernity and food

Food consumption changed during the last years worldwide as well as nationally. Most enterprises shed light on raw materials sources used because some consumers give importance to nature and organic products. Many sociologists as (Aubert, 2004, 2008; Charles & Lipovetsky, 2006; Lipovetsky, 2003, 2009) assert that we are not anymore on the era of modernism or postmodernism, we are living the hyper modernism, the individual moved from instant consumption (the pleasure of now) to projective consumption (the consequences of what I consume). Replacing the term postmodernism by hypermodernism refers to changes in the contemporary society (Aubert, 2004). Thus, the main characteristic of hypermodernity is the “excess” and overabundance of events that could not reassure thinking just the present. In this case, future is more important, acting today for a best future. The hyper modernism has been shown by the principal factor: the relationship to health. To Lipovetsky (2009) a prevention culture is showing up, based on body protection and health care, instead of pleasure and enjoyment of present, like it was remarkable before. This attitude corresponds to an obsession of well being, especially the apparition of the “homemade”. Consumers are more aware by the importance of health care, nowadays we noticed a several specialists in nutrition explain the contribution of food consumption in the body’s well being. In a difference from the past years, during the modern era, a copious and nourishing food was preferred than balanced meal (Lipovetsky, 2009).

For instance, a research of the Moroccan health ministry (2018) has confirmed that almost all of the respondents confirmed the importance of reducing salt consumption. 98% of respondents said that the reduction in salt consumption is quite significant to important as a measure of daily well-being (MOUNACH et al., 2018). The same research studies if the knowledge about the bad effects of salt contributes in changing habits of salt’s consumption. In other terms researchers observe if consumer’s attitude may be influenced by the type and number of information, they found that “almost 2/3 of the target population thought that they were consuming only the necessary amount of salt on a daily basis, this percentage remained high for both men and women. ¼ of the respondents, however, thought that they were consuming low to very low-salt meals on a daily basis” (MOUNACH et al., 2018,p.71) because

the target were informed that an excessive consumption of salt may cause health problems, as MOUNACH et al., (2018, p 73) attest that “The good knowledge of the target population about the harmful effect of salt was confirmed by 91.3% (90.4-92.2) who confirmed that excessive salt consumption could cause serious health problems”.

In addition of the health-care, the hypermodernism shows more interest in social action by people, Current consumption is characterized by the social influence on the attitudes of individuals, Tapia, (2012, P.19) explains by presenting the particularities of hypermodernism that it never have there been so many actions of solidarity in our society and humanitarian generosity so widely distributed in the world. In this type of behavior, the individual often intends to bring a utility or a plus to others, through his act of consumption, or to avoid having negative consequences. In our case some consumer may buy local products from cooperative just because it will generate benefit for their members, especially when the cooperative is founded by women in rural areas. Knowing this information may encourage consumers to have intention to buy local products from cooperatives.

Another factor may influence the attitude of consumers toward local products is the nostalgia. These are today systematically developed by "retro-marketing" whose objective is to promote affective brands playing on consumers' nostalgia. The combination of cultures and encroachment of industrial consumption reminds the nostalgic of nature and authentic products (Ferrandi, 2013; Lipovetsky, 2009). This subject is noted by seniors' consumers who lived these experiences, called: «childhood memories». In this case, the consumers having the experience of consumption act, giving them pleasure, they will be involved in the information's research about where or how to find that pleasure. According to the planned behavior theory (Fishbein&Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 1985), the involvement can be preceded by the information knowledge to build a favorite consumption of natures and authentic products.

Figure 1: Diagram, made by us, explaining the process followed by consumers who have had a shopping experience.

The past became itself a consumption product as it attests the feedback to vintage style, museum visits, the evolution of typical products and ancestral. Nowadays individuals started to search for products basically made by nature's components and fewer chemical products. In Morocco, we note the advertisement is giving ahead nutritionist attributes, natural and without conservatives.

As we noticed, local products represent a very strong emotional charge and crystallize expectations as diverse as taste, health, protection of the environment, support for small producers (Fort & Fort, 2006).

The advertisements target all age categories, for youth for example who experienced the consumption of natural and authentic product, they may be purchasing involved once after getting the knowledge of these products and their advantages, for example for some persons, it can be the additional nutritious intakes, the ecologic or social participation. Once the consumers are motivated by the consumption of these products, they get involved in the process of purchasing by building a favorite attitude of these products or the inverse of that.

Figure 2: Diagram of the purchasing act process of consumers who receive the information before the experience.

The consumption of local products by occidental countries is considered as a going back to the natural and a nostalgic moment. The second phase of our research can be a confirmation of Moroccan case study, by studying Moroccan's involvement and knowledge toward the said products.

Taking consideration of globalization effect, Moroccan model of consumption can't escape the extern influence, especially occidental influence, which contributes to behaviors change of Moroccan food; we live the occidental way in African country. Nowadays, as Zirari (2020) has noticed, Moroccan consumers try to combine between pleasure and healthy aliments. They can guaranty a good feeling with a well being.

At the medical level, particularly in urban areas, this situation is explained by the sickness development called "civilization diseases", as obesity, diabetes and cardiovascular disease, note the nutritionist D. Loubaba Laraki, doctor of nutrition and health sciences. She observed that "these diseases are caused by negative changes in Moroccan's food behavior and some inherent believe of Moroccan society". In Europe, this decease has been often related to food diet. According to Loubaba Laraki (2007), it is the same case in Morocco. Overconsumption of industrial food products, having high rate of sugar, processed fats, toxic dyes, and food preservatives, involve health problems: it contributes mostly to obesity, cardiovascular disorders, cancer, and diabetes (Nestle, op. cit.: 2-3) this deceases are the principal cause of mortality in developed countries, and we should add too overfed. Food has an important impact on the human body and its functions, the bad choice of what we eat can influence, negatively, the human system (Clatici et al., 2018) both physiological and psychological one.

1.2. Local Product: Is it a cure for bipolarity of food consumption?

The diversity of food supply and taste homogeneity worldwide have impacted consumption mode in Morocco. We can find on the same breakfast table, a local olive oil, cheese from Holland, Moroccan tea, an Italian manufactured chocolate pounder, a homemade jam, French baguette or croissants, etc. Otherwise, a mixture of natural/ chemical and homemade/ manufactured products. We called that in our research study: The food bipolarity.

Local products are among the products that not only serve to fulfil the feeling of hunger, but are also characterised by several psychological and societal facets. It has been noticed in the

advertisements of local products, the promotion of authenticity, the natural ancestral skill and the environment protection. (Fort & Fort, 2006).

Local products are distinguished from generic products (other chemical products and transformed), by their identification and their attribution to territory specifics. For example, olive oil of the Tiout-Chiadma region is different from Taounate's olive oil, the same thing for honey made in the Fes-Meknes region is different from Souss Massa ones . Local products are rather symbolic goods and their success holds on their authenticity and belonging to a specific local region, therefore they maintain their tradition. Hence, we can say that these particularities give to the local products a brand, known as « collective brand ».

The industrialisation of the food sphere generates consumer anxiety, calling symbolic rural roots and affective (Poulain 1993) cited by (Zindy et al., 2018). As said before it's all about hypermodern consumer characteristics (Aubert, 2004) who's nostalgic about past and looks for authentic products. People experienced the natural product before, especially in the region of belonging, are more involved in the information search of local products.

Thus, there are numerous companies offering products based on nostalgic feelings through advertising communication, product design and their package. Due to sensory dimensions (Sirieix, 1999), the food can be a catalyst for emotions and facilitate the recall of experiences, people, places or events and, therefore, be a vector of nostalgia (Ferrandi, 2013).

Taking the case of cooperatives using terms interrelating tradition and natural sides of their products or their components throughout official sign specifics as (AOP, IGP...), or through appellations: local products, interior products, typical products, authentic products, regional products, farm products and other mixtures of terms reminds the notion of territory or locality related to food culture, collective brands, private brand, etc. (Zindy & Hauwuy, 2017). It remains to confirm the degree of knowledge of these distinctive signs and their assimilation by the Moroccan consumer.

As it is noted, local food products are still suffering from confusion with other similar concepts. While doing our interviews with Moroccan consumers, they talk about local products as being organic products and they think that cooperatives advertise for organic products, or, local products are sold locally on the ground of markets and which we find in a specific area. Basin

on the literature review, there is not a consensual definition of the concept « local products» (Aurier et al 2004).

Hence, our research investigates if these perception sources are the same as Moroccan consumers. Preliminary results, in the next part of our explanatory research, can confirm that. The knowledge and involvement: what impact role in consumer behaviour?

Consumer behaviour is the addition of all individuals act directly related to purchasing and to economic goods and services use (Engel & Blackwell, 1982). The decision made by consumers is based on processing and evaluation of the information provided, information availability of products which we desire to advertise highlights product knowledge. One of the objectives of our research is to verify whether the information concerning local products is sufficiently available and known by the Moroccan consumer.

Consumer behaviour Analysis is the basis of any marketing strategy. Any organisation needs to have knowledge of people on whom it concern, especially in an increasingly competitive environment. Such as local products substitute by industrial products.

Individual behaviour is impacted by numerous factors (sociological, psychic, economic, environmental...). To get interested in determining variables of behaviour, we must choose most important variables and take consideration of relationship between them, given the fact that they are not independent. According to ‘‘planned behaviour Theory’’ PBT (Ajzen, 1991) The main variables involved in the purchase intention are: Knowledge and involvement. In the following part, we will explain the cross-sectional relationship between both variables.

Among the impact of Knowledge and experience, many authors, as Johnson & Russo (1984) have shown that consumers having knowledge or experience of a specific product processed information deeper than consumers do not have that expertise. However they were motivated. Hence, the first type is involved in information research more than the second type who needs more knowledge to be involved. Moroccans are considered as expert in daily using local products, based on observing Moroccan gastronomy which is based on a diversity of local products and ancestral know-how, except young city dwellers who have not consumed local products before. However, when local products are certified and marketed by cooperatives, we

should investigate the knowledge of their presence before talking about their consumption by Moroccan.

Therefore, it happens that exposition of consumers to information related to the local region improves significantly his expectations compared to other more neutral product information. However, at the same time, local information is not enough to maintain expectation levels during the global judgement: the difference between informed hedonic assessment and blind hedonic assessment.

**Figure 2 : Basic model to evaluate local food products
(Inspired by the classic "stimuli-response" approach)**

The involvement reflects the process and the behavioral nature, set up by the individual in response to external stimuli (purchasing context, the products, etc.) or intern (its values, the self-concept, etc.), and materialised when choosing by information research more intense or making decision of purchase. The most common definition of the involvement is proposed by Rothschild (1984, p. 217), which indicate that each unobservable state of motivation, of excitement or interest that cannot be measured directly is considered as involvement. Likewise, measuring or identifying the level of individual's involvement serves to identify the motivation and attitude of consumers toward a product concerned.

As it is shown in figure4, looking for information depends on numerous individuals and environmental factors. (Engel et al., 1990) affirmed that there are three characteristics of information retrieval: its intensity (the information quality and time given to this research), its orientation (research subject: products, stores, brands, sources, etc.) and the sequence of steps for this search (the order of the information).

Bettman (1979) distinguishes between two types of information retrieval depending on the objective: a permanent search for information triggered by a general interest carried by an individual in a subject or a product and having as an objective the improvement of his knowledge, and research linked to a purchase decision which, for its part, has a purchase.

2. Research methodology and Results

2.1 Methodology

Our research is under a doctoral thesis guideline, we achieved some research on the knowledge level and involvement intensity of Moroccans toward local products, in order to dissect the factors influencing the consumption and purchase of said products.

To get a significant finding, we employed qualitative methodology by individual interviews. This choice is due to, on the one hand, the few number of the Moroccan researches referring to this phenomenon (consumer behaviour of local product) and in the other hands, studying the consumer behaviour needs a deep comprehension of “how” and “why” of each believes and attitude. In other words, it considered as a newly known area, we investigate to find out answers to why and how Moroccan consumer is involved or not in purchasing the local product, such as olive oil. Besides, an interview allows observing interviewers, the verbal and nonverbal, since we are interested in psychological factors, called implicit motivations.

First of all, we led research by observing non-participating observational study which consists of knowing closely the opinion of cooperatives, who market and produce local products, on state strategies and problems experienced, and this with 30 cooperatives at the National Agadir Salon of Local Products “SNAPT” and the International Agriculture Fair of Meknes “SIAM”. Secondly, we opted for interview guides with the managers of the local products division of the Moroccan Ministry of Agriculture and with consumers. Before studying the level of knowledge and involvement of the consumers toward the local products in Morocco, it’s important to check out and list the strategies and efforts made by each part concerned by the valorization of those products.

Concerning the choice of sample size has followed the saturation principle explained by (Glaser & Strauss, 2017,p.61): «The theoretical saturation is reached when we no longer find additional information capable of enriching the theory. Consequently, it is impossible to know a priori what will be the amount of observation units required ». As already mentioned, the Moroccan state has taken several measures to enhance and protect local products, in terms of

laws and subsidies. However, are Moroccan consumers aware of these efforts? Since 2008, the policies for protection and enhancement of local products become vigilant, we started to publicise it, however, 12 years have not been enough to get Moroccan closer to Green Morocco Plan (GMP) strategy, that what we will be detailed and proven as follows.

The second part of the exploratory study is carried out by semi-structured interviews to explore the mode of consumption of the local products of our sample, on the one hand, and their knowledge on the level of local products, on the other hand.

For this, the interviews were based on the item collected by the FCQ (Food Choice Questionnaire). The quantitative motivational approach has been widely used in food science since a reliable and valid measurement instrument was proposed (Stephoe et al., 1995).

The FCQ is a battery of 36 items intended, to capture the nine motivational areas of food: Health / mood / Services associated with food / Sensory expectations / The natural nature of the food / Economic constraint / Weight control / Familiarity / Ethical concerns.

It has been applied to many varied samples in many countries over the world such as studies directed by (e.g Benda-Prokeinová & Hanová, 2016; Eertmans et al., 2006; Fotopoulos et al., 2009; Januszewska et al., 2011; Lindeman & Väänänen, 2000; Markovina et al., 2015; Marquis, 2005; Pollard et al., 1998; Prescott et al., 2002; Steptoe et al., 1995).

Studies on organic products and local products have kept only 5 motivations, namely: natural components - nutritional intake - environmental protection - sensory expectations - price.

Our observatory study based on semi-structured interview guides with heads of households and visitors to SIAM¹, SNAPT² and the agriculture fair of Chefchaouen: can confirm the presence of these five main motivations, but with different preferences, as the limited interest in the factor of environmental protection and participation in the social development of cooperatives. Thus, nutriment intake and natural components come first, followed by trust in the origin of belonging and then the price.

We conducted interviews with 30 consumers, split according to two variables: gender and family situation. This number was the result of the saturation principle (Glaser and Strauss 1967); we stopped recruiting participants when the answers became the same. The interview guide of this first research included several categories of questions about: consumption habits, belonging to the place of production, presence on the charity side,

¹ *International exhibition of agriculture in Meknes*

² *The National exhibition of local products in Agadir.*

awareness of healthy nutrition, knowledge of agricultural strategies in Morocco, level of education, etc.

Figure 3: The repartition of the interviews' participants until saturation of the responses.

Subsequently to the observatory study and the stereotype known in Morocco, about the role of women in the alimentation, women are more present in our study than men. The participants affirmation were like: “it’s the women who cared about the alimentation of the family” or “my mum/my wife who cooks for us, she’s the one who decide what to buy and what we should eat”.

2.2. Results and discussion:

To process this qualitative data, a thematic analysis was carried out based on the items of the FCQ and the links, explained in the literature review, between the knowledge and the involvement of the consumers of local products.

At the start of our interview, after the presentation, we have focused on evaluating the level of the interviewees’ knowledge toward the local product in general, and those promoted by the cooperatives. This helps up to identify if the Moroccan state’s efforts are considered by the consumers. Then, we aimed to verify if the alimentation habits have changed, to become healthy ones. As explained, above, in literature review.

In the following table, some examples of verbatim will be presented on each theme.

Table1: An outline of the thematic analysis. (by the authors)

Themes	Example of verbatim	Observation
Regions of each product	"...Argan, Honey, Saffron in Souss-Massa..."; "fig, prickly pear, Argan, olives"; "Meknes / olives, Midelt / Apples, Argan in Souss-Massa and each region is known by a specific product."	The most products cited are Olives and Argan and Saffron. And each interviewer starts by the product of his region.
State strategies (GMP)	"I have heard about this plan, but I have not seen anything on the reality"; " No, I don't know this plan"; "this plan was made to help the small agriculture... but it's not the case."	The majority doesn't hear about the strategies of the GMP. And those who know them don't believe in it.
Labelling	"...No, I don't know those labels"; " No, I have never seen them"; " I have seen them before, but I don't know their meaning"; " of course I know them but I don't trust anything from the state";	The labels "IGP" and "AOP" are not known yet by most of the interviewers and don't trust them. The minority attests the importance of them, especially to identify the origin of the product.
Nutrition Facts	"I use to buy the local product because of their nutriment component"; "olive oil has a lot of nutriments..."; "the local product is healthy"; " it's good for health especially for my children"; " I started to care about healthy aliments after being a mum..."	The principal factor influencing the consummation of the local products is their nutriments. Because they are natural, and nutritional specialists had attested it.
Packaging	"I don't care about the packaging"; "I think good package will just raise the price"; " I'd prefer an aesthetic packaging with information on it"; " I can't imagine olive oil on small bottles"; "I use to make the oil in big glass or clay bottles."; " of course I'd like to have all information on the packaging...especially the origin and the component."	For the olive's oil, the packaging is not really important. For the other products interviewers care about the packaging if the price is reasonable. It turned out that seniors do not demand compliance with packaging standards and they don't trust everything that is

		written on them. Contrary to the young interviewers, they used to read what's written on the packaging.
Taste	"olive's oil is tasty"; "I eat the local products because they are delicious"; "each olive's oil has its specific taste"; "the local product is tasty because they are natural."	The main factor influencing the consumption of the olive's oil and other local products, in general, is the taste. This attribute is due to the natural and the freshness aspects of those products.
Price	"The local products of cooperatives are expensive"; "I can pay a little more if the quality is guaranteed"; "...for me it's because those cooperatives the price of the Argan oil became too expensive...".	The greater part of the interviewees affirm that the price is the first criterion of choice from cooperatives, the other remaining say that they are ready to pay a little more, because the local products are natural, and to help the families in need.
Confidence	"I need to know the seller of the product"; "I trust on the person"; "I don't trust in cooperatives"; "Someone has to recommend the cooperative..."; "I have to try the product by myself..."; "The Moroccan Green Plan! Do you really trust on this?"	The entire interviewers trust the seller or the person who has tried the product. For the olive's oil there are some people who prefer to buy the olives and grind it by himself.
Religion	"Our prophet Mohamed PBUH ³ had advised us to eat olive oil and use it in body massage"; "olives, dates, fig...and other local products are cited in the Quran, that's why I eat them a lot."; "I use to buy the dates and fig a lot during Ramadan (month)."	The religion in Morocco is even influencing the alimentation. As a cultural factor, religion affects the consumption of the local product, especially the olive's oil and dates.

³ Peace be upon him

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<p>Habits/ Nostalgia</p>	<p>“Since my childhood I used to consume olive oil, especially in breakfast with bread”; “olive oil is daily present on our table”; “sometimes I like to eat olive oil with warm bread and tea...it’s remained me my childhood with my grandparent.”; “the smell of local products always brings memories with the nature...of course if they are natural.”</p>	<p>The olive’s oil is almost consumed by all Moroccans; it’s used to eat it with bread, to cook and like a cure for some disease. It’s linked to the alimentation culture in Morocco “just bread with olive’s oil and tea are enough to be full up!” The sensory expectation is highly present.</p>
<p>Social</p>	<p>“The modesty and simplicity of the women who worked in the cooperatives that encourage me to buy from them, it’s a social act to help them.” (Mother, Meknes); “I’d love to help, it’s with pleasure. But when I’m not sure that the poor women who produced the product will benefit from the whole money I prefer to buy from direct producers in the village than from cooperatives.”</p>	<p>As noticed before, the two items referred to social and environmental factors are not cited by the entire interviewer. Just few ones use to buy from small cooperatives or direct farmers to encourage them.</p>

To sum up the table below, we can say that the Moroccan consumer needs to be awarded by the presence and the importance of the labelled local products.

Concerning the Consumer's knowledge, only the interviewees who operate in the agricultural sector are aware of the Green Moroccan Plan strategies, the labeling, and the various local products. While, the others do not know the meaning of those labels. The minority had already heard of the PMV but do not know its strategies and obviously the majority of the interviewees, and more precisely the mothers, have no idea about these strategies and they had a hard time understand what a local product is from the start of the interview. "...I think we are not alerted by those strategies enough, the state should make effort in promotion the Moroccan products..." (young couple, Casablanca)

In this thematic we have asked the participants of their sources of knowledge, for example:

The majority of the interviewers had never seen ads on TV just when the International the International Agricultural Exhibition in Morocco approach and then they started to talk about some of the "*Terroir*" product of Morocco. Some of the interviewers have already seen some TV Shows about the cooperatives that produce the said products. "*No, I have never seen ads about the local products...just some documentary about cooperatives*" (mother, Casablanca). Another important point is the lack of diversification in the communication mix "I don't watch TV anymore...the Moroccan channels are boring" (young couple, Temara).

All of the interviewers are informed about the local product, especially the olive oil and dates, from their relatives such as family and colleagues. So they trust people they know more than cooperatives or other merchants. Just in case, those relatives have already tried cooperative products. A large part of interviewers do not use to buy from cooperatives, except during trade fair visit events which are annually. The reason is high price products and lack of proximity to cooperatives.

It's clear that the vast majority of consumers are not aware, either, about the "terroir" products' strategies, neither, the cooperatives that product and promote them. Which explains the low level of involvement towards the olive's oil promoted by cooperatives. Instead of that, a high level of involvement is remarked toward olive's oil of informal sellers.

The majority of the participants in our studies clearly prefer national and regional products because these products are not only consumed for their concrete benefits, but also for their hedonistic values. By buying or consuming regional products, consumers identify with the region of these products. Consequently, the State must invest further in raising awareness of

local products by attributing them to their regions of origin, so that Moroccans become aware of the diversity of local products in Morocco. Most of our interviewees confirmed their return to natural products for health reasons. They are trying to consume less and less chemicals. Especially the mothers attest that they started consuming olive's oil to prevent from diseases or to replace some aliments such as butter or sunflower oil “ because of the high level of cholesterol I replaced the butter by the olive's oil...”(mother, Fes) , “ Since I knew that the olive's oil had numerous nutritional facts more than other types of oil, I started to cook just with it...also we started to consume it daily in the breakfast” (mother, Casablanca); “ being a mum I care, more, about what I should prepare for my children... that's why I use the olive's oil more than before” (mother, Temara).

Referring to the link explained, up above, between the knowledge and the involvement toward a product, when the consumer knows a merchant of the olive's oil and had tried before, he's automatically encouraged to buy it. In contrast with the cooperatives, if they don't know whether their presence neither the quality of their products, it will be difficult to be having an intention to buy their products.

Figure 4 : The influence of knowledge in involvement

Conclusion

According to sociologist Lipovetsky G. (2004), the manifestation of hyper modernism is reflected in particular by the essential factor of hypermodernity: the relationship to health. We have entered a culture of prevention that privileges the protection of our body and our health more than the enjoyment of the present moment.

However, in recent years (as a result of the food crises) confidence, which used to be widespread, has become more hypothetical despite the fact that food safety has never performed so well in terms of technology. Consumer concern therefore seems to emanate more from symbolic principles than from rational or objective ones. Health crises have led to a sense of mistrust and uncertainty among consumers, who take refuge behind typical and authentic products. Emotional and identity characteristics impact the value of local products, they relate it to territories such as product origin and belonging feeling, in addition to the knowledge of the name on territory and potentially granted associations to it.

This opens up interesting prospects in terms of segmentation, making it possible to sell territories and local products based on their geographic identification, and the enhancement of the qualities of each local product. Moroccan territories are not lacking in potentials. Hence, it can be developed progressively. This present study, in addition to other studies, agree that health is a very important aspect in consumers' perception and choice of food, staying healthy or offering a healthy meal to family members is essential in consumers' lives.

Country of origin was identified in the literature review as an important issue that could be used to influence consumer evaluation of the brand. The influence of a product's country of origin on consumer evaluations depends on several criteria: the perceived degree of relevance of this information, motivation, involvement, preference for a particular country, perceived risk, number of attributes, and the importance of origin in relation to other elements, and the ease of finding information.

Therefore, the Moroccan state will have to take advantage of the specific features of the domestic food market to position itself on the international market. Domestic production is expected to keep up with import competition and, above all, also to prosper. To guarantee the economic and social development of Moroccan regions, it is first necessary to respond to local demand and to win international markets. For this, the only way to consume locally is to produce more and better. This work is only a beginning approach to measure consumer

involvement in territorial development. Thus, it helps, on the one hand, on identifying the level of Moroccan's knowledge, and in the other hand, identifying the needs and requirements regarding the consumption of these products. This can help to propose strategies to promote local products and by identifying needs consequently, this study opens up a very stimulating field of research around the links between the territory, the local product, the consumer and the interest of labelling in general. Knowing the factors that stimulate the consumption of local products will imply the promotion of these products from their territory and the success of each entity that has a direct or near relationship with these products. In other words, promoting local products will allow local, regional and national development in Morocco.

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